

OutAdvEd - Method and Tool to Evaluate the Course Modules and Micro-Modules

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Technical sheet

Title: OutAdvEd – Method and Tool to Evaluate the Course Modules and Micro-Modules

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<https://www.outdoor-adventure-education.eu/>

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1 Introduction

Evaluation studies provide a valuable method for systematically assessing the effectiveness of programmes, projects, and research initiatives. The purpose of this evaluation was to collect and analyse data related to the Outdoor Adventure Education (OAE) programme implemented during the Learning and Teaching Training (LTT) event in Seville, Spain. The focus was placed on both the implementation of the LTT event and the perceived quality and relevance of the developed teaching modules.

For this purpose, specifically designed questionnaires were administered to two target groups: physical education (PE) educators and preservice teacher students. The evaluation tools were based on established instruments developed in previous Erasmus+ projects (e.g., BMC-EU, PRIME PETE, EduPASS) and were adapted to suit the context and objectives of the current project.

The overall purpose of this evaluation process is to provide insights into the strengths and weaknesses of the event and the teaching modules, identify areas for improvement, and support informed decisions (e.g., planning, design, development, and delivery) regarding the future implementation of these modules. Additionally, the developed OAE evaluation tools will be used in the following R (i.e., R6), which is the evaluation study and respective report. Furthermore, the method and tool(s) can be used in future, similar evaluation procedures. Lastly, the findings are intended to contribute to the broader field of Outdoor Adventure Education research, with a specific focus on fostering social and emotional outcomes for participating students and stakeholders involved in similar educational initiatives.

2 Event Evaluation

2.1 Educators' Evaluation of the LTT event

OUTADVED PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT EVENT EVALUATION FOR EDUCATORS

Please help enhance the quality of the student teacher event by spending a few minutes completing this questionnaire.

Participation in this study is voluntary. All information provided will be confidential and participants' anonymity will be protected throughout the study. IP addresses will not be collected at any point, meaning the data you provide cannot be traced back to the participant. The results of the evaluation process will be published without sharing any information about the respondents in an open access publication in the frame of the OutAdvEd European project.

Part 1: General Information

1. Do you agree to complete this questionnaire?

- I agree
- I do not agree

2. Anonymous Code (first 3 letters of your first name + day of birth)

Example: Christian, 19 May → CHR/19

Answer: _____

3. What is your age?

Answer: _____

4. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

5. University / Faculty / Department / Organization

- University of Luxembourg
- University of Sevilla
- HUMAK
- Masaryk University
- National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
- Other: _____

6. Your Profession:

- Teacher Educator
- School Teacher
- Outdoor Education Instructor

7. Year of experiences at Primary or Secondary Level

Answer: _____

8. Year of experiences at Third Level Initial Teacher Education

Answer: _____

9. The Study Programme you mainly teaching in:

- Bachelor
- Master
- Other

10. The Teacher Programme you mainly teaching in is:

- Specialist PE Teacher
- Generalist Teacher
- Generalist Teacher with PE Specialism
- Outdoor Instructor
- Other

11. Do you lead or have you recently given any Outdoor Adventure Education training/courses?

- Yes
- No

If yes, please describe briefly what this training/course is or was about?

Answer: _____

Part 2: Professional Development Event Feedback

2.1 Please rate your level of agreement with the following statements:

Statement	Disagree	Rather Disagree	Neutral	Rather Agree	Agree	N/A
The event was adequately and logically structured.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The event was well designed.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The timeframe of the event was appropriate.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The event was delivered at an appropriate pace/rhythm.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The materials and resources were well prepared.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The content was presented in a clear and understandable way.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The teaching enabled me to attain the learning outcomes.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The overall topic was relevant to my practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The specific content was relevant to my practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The topics were discussed sufficiently.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I improved my knowledge and skills.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

The content will be helpful to me as a teacher.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The teaching units are compatible with the national curriculum.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I gained new knowledge/information for my practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The content was new to me.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I enjoyed the event.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

2.2 Statements about implementation and feasibility:

Statement	Disagree	Rather Disagree	Neutral	Rather Agree	Agree	N/A
The event motivated me to consider implementing the contents in my teaching.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I will use the materials and resources which I received in the event in my lessons and future career as a teacher.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I can imagine myself implementing OutAdvEd Project examples in my future career as a teacher.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

I consider the OutAdvEd Project examples useful as they can be easily implemented during teaching.

2.3 Would you recommend this event to your peers and other educators?

1 2 3 4 5 (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

The **BEST** features of the Professional development event were:

I did **NOT** like the following:

I would like to see the following **CHANGES**:

I have specific comments for this Professional development event:

Thank you for your participation!

Your feedback will contribute to improving future professional development opportunities in Outdoor Adventure Education.

2.2 Students' Evaluation of the LTT event

OUTADVED PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT EVENT EVALUATION FOR STUDENTS

Purpose:

Please help enhance the quality of the student-teacher event by completing this short questionnaire. Participation is voluntary and anonymous. No personal data (like IP addresses) will be collected. The findings will be published anonymously as part of the OutAdvEd European Project.

Part 1: General Information

1. Do you agree to complete this questionnaire?

- I agree
- I do not agree

2. Anonymous Code (first 3 letters of your first name + day of birth)

Example: Christian, 19 May → CHR/19

Answer: _____

3. What is your age?

Answer: _____

4. What is your gender?

- Male

- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

5. University / Faculty / Department / Organization

- University of Luxembourg
- University of Sevilla
- HUMAK
- Masaryk University
- National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
- Other: _____

6. Your Study Programme / Degree:

- Bachelor
- Master

7. Your Teacher Programme:

- Specialist PE Teacher
- Generalist Teacher
- Generalist Teacher with PE Specialism
- Other: _____

8. Year of Studies:

Answer: _____

9. Have you previously attended any Outdoor Adventure Education training/course?

- Yes
- No

Part 2: Professional Development Event Feedback

2.1 Please rate your level of agreement with the following statements:

Statement	Disagree	Rather Disagree	Neutral	Rather Agree	Agree	N/A
The event was adequately and logically structured.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The event was well designed.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The timeframe of the event was appropriate.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The event was delivered at an appropriate pace/rhythm.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The materials and resources were well prepared.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The content was presented in a clear and understandable way.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The teaching enabled me to attain the learning outcomes.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The overall topic was relevant to my practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The specific content was relevant to my practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

The topics were discussed sufficiently.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I improved my knowledge and skills.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The content will be helpful to me as a teacher.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The teaching units are compatible with the national curriculum.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I gained new knowledge/information for my practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The content was new to me.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I enjoyed the event.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

2.2 Statements about implementation and feasibility:

Statement	Disagree	Rather Disagree	Neutral	Rather Agree	Agree	N/A
The event motivated me to apply the content in my teaching.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
I will use the resources from this event in my future teaching.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

I can imagine using OutAdvEd examples in my future career.

The OutAdvEd examples are useful and easy to implement.

2.3 Would you recommend this event to your peers and other educators?

1 2 3 4 5 (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

The **BEST** features of the Professional development event were:

I did **NOT** like the following:

I would like to see the following **CHANGES**:

I have specific comments for this Professional development event:

Thank you for your participation!

Your feedback will contribute to improving future professional development opportunities in Outdoor Adventure Education.

3 Teaching Units Evaluation

3.1 Educators' evaluation of the teaching units

OUTADVED TEACHING UNIT EVALUATION FOR EDUCATORS

Purpose:

Please help enhance the quality of our teaching units by spending a few minutes completing this questionnaire.

Participation in this study is voluntary. All information provided will be confidential and participants' anonymity will be protected throughout the study. IP addresses will not be collected at any point, meaning the data you provide cannot be traced back to the participant. The results of the evaluation process will be published without sharing any information about the respondents in an open access publication in the frame of the OutAdvEd European project.

Part 1: General Information

1. Do you agree to complete this questionnaire?

- I agree
- I do not agree

2. University / Faculty / Department / Organization

- University of Luxembourg
- University of Sevilla

- HUMAK
- Masaryk University
- National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
- Other: _____

For anonymity and coding purposes, please use the following coding system: The first THREE letters of the FIRST name and DATE of birth. Example - Christian, 19 May 1982 = CHR/19)*

Answer: _____

Date:

Answer: _____

Teaching unit evaluation tool

To ensure the quality of the teaching unit content as well as improving it, we kindly ask you to answer the following questions. Please select the most relevant answer.

Teaching unit Title: _____

Indicate your level of satisfaction with each of the following items by selecting the most relevant answer.

2.1 Please rate your level of agreement with the following statements:

Statement	Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very satisfied	N/A
The delivery of the teaching unit (e.g., lectures, practical sessions, group discussions, sharing of ideas and experiences, etc.).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The pedagogical approaches presented to teaching OutAdvEd.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The content of the teaching unit.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The clarity of the teaching unit content.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The balance between theory and practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

The appropriateness of the assignments.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The explanation of the assessment criteria.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The assessment methods effectiveness in identifying my strengths and areas for future development.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The communication of the learning outcomes and assessment model.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The collaboration through shared knowledge with peers.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The overall workload (achievable, realistic, adequate).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The relevance of the teaching unit to raising my professional development (knowledge and practice).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The transferability of the lessons learnt in the teaching unit to practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The development of new skills and/or teaching strategies due to this teaching unit.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The increase of my motivation to learn due to this teaching unit.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

The overall knowledge gained by the teaching unit.

My overall satisfaction with the teaching unit.

I would recommend this teaching unit to other teaching staff.

1 2 3 4 5 (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

Comments about the teaching unit

To help improve the quality of the learning experience it is very helpful to receive additional qualitative feedback. The following questions will help staff and future sport educators. Please attempt to answer as many questions as you can. You can include anything about the teaching unit that you think is relevant.

The **BEST** features of the teaching unit were:

I did **NOT** like the following:

I would like to see the following CHANGES:

I have specific comments for this teaching unit:

I will try to implement these teaching unit's topics (**maximum 3**) in my practice:

3.2 Students' evaluation of the teaching units

OUTADVED TEACHING UNIT EVALUATION FOR STUDENTS

Purpose:

Please help enhance the quality of our teaching units by spending a few minutes completing this questionnaire.

Participation in this study is voluntary. All information provided will be confidential and participants' anonymity will be protected throughout the study. IP addresses will not be collected at any point, meaning the data you provide cannot be traced back to the participant. The results of the evaluation process will be published without sharing any information about the respondents in an open access publication in the frame of the OutAdvEd European project.

Part 1: General Information

Do you agree to complete this questionnaire?

- I agree
- I do not agree

University / Faculty / Department / Organization

- University of Luxembourg
- University of Sevilla
- HUMAK
- Masaryk University

National and Kapodistrian University of Athens

Other: _____

For anonymity and coding purposes, please use the following coding system: The first THREE letters of the FIRST name and DATE of birth. Example - Christian, 19 May 1982 = CHR/19)*

Answer: _____

Date:

Answer: _____

Teaching unit evaluation tool

To ensure the quality of the teaching unit content as well as improving it, we kindly ask you to answer the following questions. Please select the most relevant answer.

Teaching unit Title: _____

Indicate your level of satisfaction with each of the following items by selecting the most relevant answer.

2.1 Please rate your level of agreement with the following statements:

Statement	Very dissatis fied	Dissati sfied	Neutra l	Satisfi ed	Very satisfi ed	N/A
The delivery of the teaching unit (e.g., lectures, practical sessions, group discussions, sharing of ideas and experiences, etc.).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The pedagogical approaches presented to teaching OutAdvEd.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The content of the teaching unit.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The clarity of the teaching unit content.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The balance between theory and practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The appropriateness of the assignments.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The explanation of the assessment criteria.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The assessment methods effectiveness in identifying my strengths and areas for future development.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The communication of the learning outcomes and assessment model.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

The collaboration through shared knowledge with peers.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The overall workload (achievable, realistic, adequate).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The relevance of the teaching unit to raising my professional development (knowledge and practice).	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The transferability of the lessons learnt in the teaching unit to practice.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The development of new skills and/or teaching strategies due to this teaching unit.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The increase of my motivation to learn due to this teaching unit.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
The overall knowledge gained by the teaching unit.	<input type="checkbox"/>					
My overall satisfaction with the teaching unit.	<input type="checkbox"/>					

I would recommend this teaching unit to other students and future educators.

1 2 3 4 5 (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree)

Comments about the teaching unit

To help improve the quality of the learning experience it is very helpful to receive additional qualitative feedback. The following questions will help staff and future sport educators. Please attempt to answer as many questions as you can. You can include anything about the teaching unit that you think is relevant.

The **BEST** features of the teaching unit were:

I did **NOT** like the following:

I would like to see the following **CHANGES**:

I have specific comments for this teaching unit:

I will try to implement these teaching unit's topics (**maximum 3**) in my practice: